

With this RFI NIH seeks input on use cases, expectations, and capabilities to enhance NIH-wide data discovery and its reuse. In particular, NIH would like to better understand researchers' experiences and expectations to identify underlying barriers or opportunities that can move the search landscape forward. Our perspective as data integrators across the translational spectrum is shown below for each of the search activities in scope (cohort-building, knowledge based search, and primary dataset discovery).

		Findable	Accessible	Interoperable	Reusable			
			Traceable	Licensed	Connected			
Cohort-building	Barrier	No central tool inventory across clinical and translational sites, patient registries, etc.	Unusable behind firewalls or non-standard release mechanisms ePHI data is difficult to share efficiently and appropriately	APIs, when available do not conform to the same standard, or to any	Narrow consents, IP challenges	Poor documentation, provenance, attribution	Undeclared, opaque, restrictive, inconsistent, incompatible, or undeclared. Heavy negotiation required.	Lack of standards, or even forethought around cohort descriptions
	Opportunity	Create standards around definitions of cohorts; share abstracted views and create tools that integrate these views. When creating searchable descriptions from existing data, do not rely on string matching alone. First leverage named entity recognition (NER) — a form of Natural Language Processing (NLP) — whereby key terminology concepts can be recognized. Leverage the NER results (preferably validated) with semantically-aware (reasoner-enabled) search tools. Require all cohorts assembled with federal funding to be registered where appropriate	Assembling cohorts often requires multi-institutional cooperation; therefore it is important to improve investigator onboarding processes through federated authentication and improved governance mechanisms. Resource sharing plan*	Create standards for cohort APIs. Improve e-consent standards so that data / cohorts can be more easily assembled. Codify procedures for re-consenting patients, or recruiting for trials, so that the process is both clear and efficient.	Implement e-consent more broadly, and improve granularity of permissions so that evolving consent forms can be properly and efficiently honored retrospectively. Improve basic tooling for creating and managing registries and cohorts. Provide support for migrating existing data to more modern tools. Many tools that exist are aging and also not easily generalized to other conditions.	Improve identifier hygiene throughout the cohort management cycle, from participant identifiers, through to studies, institutions and more. Invest in ways to match patients that may be present in multiple registries / providers (eg. PPRL, or patient IDs). Improve training around ethical implications of mixing consented and unconsented data.	Enforce data licensing Resource sharing plan*	Prospectively improve identifier hygiene and tooling at the data capture stage for key pieces of data that would be potential search terms (such as diagnoses, drugs, symptoms) Develop, improve migration tools for legacy data.
Knowledge-Based Search	Barrier	Although very good tools now exist for looking up knowledge about entities (eg. ensembl, uniprot, ncbigene, etc), researchers don't necessarily know about all the tools that could be useful to them and may not necessarily be inclined to search for them either.	Knowledge resources do not typically suffer from accessibility issues	Knowledgebases are poorly interoperable, posing challenges to knowledge engineering	Difficulty reusing portions of an overall knowledgebase	Poor documentation, provenance, attribution	Undeclared, opaque, restrictive, inconsistent, incompatible, or undeclared. Heavy negotiation required.	Sources of reference knowledge tend to be siloed
	Opportunity	Improve outreach, especially to trainees		Improve annotation with ontologies	Encourage exports and/or APIs that enable users to retrieve key slices of the data.	Improve attribution of underlying data from original sources.	Enforce data licensing Resource sharing plan*	develop knowledge graphs that integrate knowledge from multiple sources
Data Set Discovery	Barrier	Time consuming & expensive to find, poor indexing Very heterogeneous use cases require very different dataset descriptions to make search work	Balance privacy with open methods; ePHI is difficult to share	Infrequent/different use of means data is not comparable & consistent	Cleaning of published primary data is done by multiple actors, but the results of that cleaning are not available more broadly.	Attribution instructions lacking, provenance underspecified	Undeclared, opaque, restrictive, inconsistent, incompatible, or undeclared. Heavy negotiation required.	Disconnected stale clinical data, siloed from basic research
	Opportunity	Define the use cases for search and the priorities thereof. Create data descriptions that support these use cases. Favor descriptions and standards that support multiple use cases and also result in metadata that can be crawled by public search engines eg. via schema.org.	Define best practices and tooling to improve the efficiency and quality of data governance. Consider discoverability and accessibility as a first citizen in the dataset generation process. (see resource sharing plan)	Harmonize standard data models for data likely to be queried in the same context. Develop non-lossy, fully provenanced and validated mappings between models.	Enable the results of prior data cleaning efforts to be discoverable and reusable.	Improve attribution of underlying data from original sources. Improve provenance of mappings between data models.	Enforce data licensing Resource sharing plan*	Provide better support, training, and onboarding for basic researchers who have hypotheses that could be informed by observational EHR data.

***Resource sharing plan:** The resource sharing plan is key to shifting the culture toward intentional, effective resource sharing. NIH policy advances have helped, however, we strongly believe that the resource sharing plan should be a scored section of the proposals. We also believe that having more prescriptive structure to the resource sharing plan would require more thoughtfulness and enforceability, for example around licensing and distribution mechanisms. Additional thoughts on this were provided under our response to NIH RFI on updating the data sharing and management plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2302593>